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**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL COUNSELLING NEEDS OF
 SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Abstract: *The present study is an attempt to explore and compare psychological counselling needs of boys and girls secondary school students in Wardha thesil. Descriptive survey method was used in this study. The sample consists of 120 Secondary school students. For collecting data the tool 'Psychological Counselling Needs Scale' standardized by Dr. Vijayalaxmi Chauhan, Udaipur and Gunjan Arora (Ahmadabad). Mean, SD and 't'- value test was used for analysis of data. The main findings of this study are: Psychological counselling needs are Secondary school boys higher than the girls. Rural boys and girls have similar. Urban boys higher than the girls.*

Keywords: *Psychological counselling needs and secondary school Students.*

Introduction:

Educational psychology plays important role in teaching- learning process. Educational psychology guides about teaching, learning, intelligence, personality, individual differences and also needs to guidance and counselling. Every child has individual needs. Secondary level is very important for physical, social, spiritual, moral and intellectual development of students. Secondary Education imparted by schools, teachers, parents and society helps an individual to live a balanced life. But; today's students face the most of problems like educational, social, financial and psychological etc. Students do not focus on own study and getting complex in educational and social life.

To understand the student's problems and their needs it's important to counselling to them. Counselling is needed to help the students for achievement and adjustment in the various situations in life. Counselling may enable the student to acquire new understandings, skills, competency, thinking, humanity and strategies that make them better to handle similar problems in life.

Definition of Counselling

Ruth Strong - Counselling is a face to face relationship in which growth takes place in the counselor as well as the counselee.

Myers - Counselling means a relationship between two persons in which one person provides special assistance to the others.

So counselling is most important for students for individual development. That is why researcher tents to find out the psychological counselling needs of secondary school students.

Statement of the Problem

A comparative study of psychological counselling needs of secondary school students.

Objectives

1. To study the psychological counselling needs of boys and girls Secondary school students.
2. To compare the psychological counselling needs of boys and girls secondary school students.
3. To compare the psychological counselling needs of rural and urban secondary school students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of rural secondary school students.
3. There is no significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of urban secondary school students.

Method of the Study:

Descriptive survey method was used for the present study. The population for the study includes all the students of Secondary school of Wardha Tehsil. In the present study researcher has chosen 4 Secondary school by lottery method from the list of secondary school of Wardha tehsil. In which 2 schools were rural and 2 were urban and then researcher has chosen 120 students with the help of purposive sampling as under.

The following tools were used to collect the data from secondary School student from Wardha city in District (Maharashtra) Psychological Counselling Needs Scale standardized by Dr. Vijayalaxmi Chauhan, Udaipur and Gunjan Arora (Ahmadabad). The following statistical techniques were employed to test the hypotheses of the study:

- Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value.

Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Descriptive Analysis

School	Students	N	Mean	SD
Rural	Boys	30	67.93	8.33
	Girls	30	65.04	9.01
Urban	Boys	30	66.32	7.11
	Girls	30	62.33	7.44

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis no. 01: There is no significant difference in psychological counseling needs between boys and girls of secondary school students.

Table No. 01

Secondary school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Boys	60	67.12	7.72	118	1.98	2.23	Rejected
Girls	60	63.88	8.22				

From the results of Table No. 01, it can be seen that, the boys and girls secondary school is differ significantly with respect to psychological counselling need ($t=2.23$, $p>0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 't' value; we can say that, there is significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of secondary school students. Finding: Indicating that the boys higher psychological counselling needs than the girls of secondary school.

Hypothesis no. 02: There is no significant difference in psychological counseling needs between boys and girls of rural secondary school students.

Table No. 02

Rural Secondary school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Boys	30	67.93	8.33	58	2.00	0.93	Accepted
Girls	30	65.04	9.01				

From the results of Table No. 02, it can be seen that, the boys and girls rural secondary school do not differ significantly with respect to psychological counselling need ($t=0.93$, $p<0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the basis of obtain 't' value; we can say that, There is no significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of rural secondary school students. Finding: Indicating that the rural secondary school boys and girls students have similar psychological counseling needs.

Hypothesis no. 03: There is no significant difference in psychological counseling needs between boys and girls of rural secondary school students.

Table No. 03

Urban Secondary school	N	Mean	SD	df	Table 't'	Obtained 't'	Accept/ Rejected
Boys	30	66.32	7.11	58	2.00	2.13	Rejected
Girls	30	62.33	7.44				

From the results of Table No. 02, it can be seen that, the boys and girls urban secondary school is differ significantly with respect to psychological counselling need ($t=2.13$, $p>0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 't' value; we can say that, there is significant difference in psychological counselling needs between boys and girls of rural secondary school students. Finding: Indicating that the urban secondary school boys higher psychological counselling needs than the girls of urban secondary school.

Major Findings:

1. Secondary school boys higher psychological counselling needs than the girls of secondary school.
2. Rural secondary school boys and girls have similar psychological counselling needs.
3. Urban secondary school boys higher psychological counselling needs than the girls of urban secondary school.

Conclusion

Overall study shows that psychological counselling needs boy's and girl's secondary school student is different. School administration should see the important of arrange counselling programme in school. Effective counselling should be provided by trained counselors in every school. Schools should be used psychological test to knowing students individual needs.

Reference

1. Aggarwal J.C. (1991). Educational & Vocational Guidance & Counselling. New Delhi: Doaba House.
2. Anastasi, Anne (1988) Psychological Testing (6th Edition) London. MacMillan Publishing Company.
3. Best, J. W and Khan K. M. (2002) Research in Education (7th Edition) New Delhi, Practice Hall of India.
4. Cattell, R. B (2008) Psychological Testing, New Delhi: Srishti Book Distributors.
5. Chauhan S. S. (1978) Advance Educational Psychology, New Delhi.
6. Garrett, H. E (1985) Statistics in Psychology and Education, Bombay Vakils, Feffer and Simons Ltd.
7. Kothari, C.R. (1990) Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques, New Delhi: Wiley Eastern Limited.
8. Mangal S. K. Essential of Educational Psychological, New Delhi: MacGrow Hill Publication.
9. Sharma, R.A. (2001). Essentials of Measurement in Education and Psychology, Meerut: Surya Publication.

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